

A NOTE ON RADIAL RADIO NUMBER OF A GRAPH

Selvam Avadayappan*, M. Bhuvaneshwari** & S.Vimalajenifer***

Research Department of Mathematics, Virudhunagar Hindu Nadars' Senthikumara Nadar College,
Virudhunagar, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

Let G be any simple, connected, undirected and finite graph. A radial radio labeling, f , of G is a function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots\}$ satisfying the condition $d(u, v) + |f(u) - f(v)| \geq 1 + rad(G)$, for all $u, v \in V(G)$, where $d(u, v)$ and $rad(G)$ denote the distance between the vertices u and v and the radius of the graph G , respectively. The span of a radial radio labeling f is the largest integer in the range of f and is denoted by $span(f)$. The radial radio number of G , $rr(G)$, is the minimum span taken over all radial radio labelings of G . Denote $N_0(v) = \{v\}$, $N_\lambda(v) = \{w: d(v, w) = \lambda\}$ and $\mathcal{N}_\lambda[v] = \bigcup_{i=0}^{\lambda} N_i(v)$. In this paper, we introduce some new concepts related with the sequence of the radial radio numbers of the induced subgraphs induced by $\mathcal{N}_\lambda[v]$.

Key Words: Frequency Assignment Problem, Radius, Diameter, Radio Labeling, Radial Radio Labeling, Radio Number, Radial Radio Number & rr Sequence.

1. Introduction:

In this paper, we consider only simple, connected, undirected and finite graphs. For basic notations and terminology, we follow [2]. Let $G = (V, E)$ be a simple connected graph. A vertex $v \in V$ is called a *full vertex*, if it is adjacent to all other vertices. Let $u, v \in V$ be any two vertices of G . The *distance* $d(u, v)$ between u and v , is the length of a shortest (u, v) -path in G . For any vertex $u \in V$, the *eccentricity*, $e(u)$, of u is the distance of a vertex farthest from u . The *radius* of a graph G is the minimum eccentricity among all the vertices and is denoted by $rad(G)$. The *diameter* of G is the maximum eccentricity among all the vertices and is denoted by $diam(G)$. The relation between $rad(G)$ and $diam(G)$ is given by the inequality $rad(G) \leq diam(G) \leq 2rad(G)$ [6]. For further details on distance in graphs, one can refer [3].

For a subset S of V , let $\langle S \rangle$ denote the induced subgraph of G induced by S . A *clique* C is a subset of V with maximum number of vertices such that $\langle C \rangle$ is complete. The *clique number* of a graph G , denoted by ω , is the number of vertices in a clique of G .

For any vertex $v \in V(G)$, the *open neighborhood* $N(v)$ is the set of all vertices adjacent to v . That is, $N(v) = \{u \in V(G) : uv \in E(G)\}$. The *closed neighborhood* $N[v]$ of v is defined by $N[v] = N(v) \cup \{v\}$. Denote $N_0(v) = \{v\}$, $N_\lambda(v) = \{w: d(v, w) = \lambda\}$ and $\mathcal{N}_\lambda[v] = \bigcup_{i=0}^{\lambda} N_i(v)$.

In 1960's Rosa [11] introduced the concept of graph labeling. A *graph labeling* is an assignment of numbers to the vertices or edges or both, satisfying some constraint. Rosa named the labeling introduced by him as β -*valuation* and later on it becomes a very famous interesting graph labeling called *graceful labeling*, which is the origin for any graph labeling problem. Motivated by real life problems, many mathematicians introduced various labeling concepts [8]. Here, we see one of the familiar graph labelings in graph theory.

The problem of assigning frequencies to the channels for the FM radio stations is known as *Frequency Assignment Problem* (FAP). This problem was studied by W. K. Hale [9]. In a telecommunication system, the assignment of channels to FM radio stations play a vital role. Motivated by the FAP, Chartrand et al., [4] introduced the concept of radio labeling. For a given k , $1 \leq k \leq diam(G)$, a *radio k -coloring*, f , is an assignment of positive integers to the vertices satisfying the following condition:

$$d(u, v) + |f(u) - f(v)| \geq 1 + k \quad (1)$$

for all $u, v \in V$. Whenever, $diam(G) = k$, the radio k -coloring is called a *radio labeling* [5] of G . The *span* of a radio labeling f is the largest integer in the range of f and is denoted by $span(f)$. The *radio number* of G is the minimum span taken over all radio labelings of G and is denoted by $rn(G)$.

Motivated by the work of Chartrand et al., on radio labeling, KM. Kathiresan and S. Vimalajenifer [10] introduced the concept of radial radio labeling. A *radial radio labeling* f of G is a function $f: V \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots\}$ satisfying the condition,

$$d(u, v) + |f(u) - f(v)| \geq 1 + rad(G) \quad (2)$$

for all $u, v \in V$. This condition is obtained by taking $k = rad(G)$ in (1). The above condition is known as *radial radio condition*. The *span* of a radial radio labeling f is the largest integer in the range of f . The *radial radio number* is the minimum span taken over all radial radio labelings of G and is denoted by $rr(G)$. That is, $rr(G) = \min_f \max_{v \in V} f(v)$, where the minimum runs over all radial radio labelings of G .

The *centre* is the subgraph of G induced by the set of vertices of minimum eccentricity. Any graph G which is isomorphic to its centre is called a *self centered graph*. Note that in a self centered graph G , $rad(G) = diam(G)$.

Theorem 1.1: Let G be a self centered graph on n vertices. Then $rr(G) \geq n$.

Proof: Since G is self centered, $rad(G) = diam(G)$. This implies that, $rn(G) = rr(G)$. But it is already proved that, $rn(G) \geq n$ [7]. Thus we have, $rr(G) \geq n$.

Fact (1): Two vertices u and v have the same labels only when $d(u, v) \geq 1 + rad(G)$.

For, let G be a graph on n vertices and let f be a radial radio labeling of G . Then the radial radio condition for G give $d(u, v) + |f(u) - f(v)| \geq 1 + rad(G)$, for all $u, v \in V(G)$. This implies that, $|f(u) - f(v)| \geq 1 + rad(G) - d(u, v)$, for all $u, v \in V(G)$. Therefore, if $f(u) = f(v)$, then $d(u, v) \geq 1 + rad(G)$. In this paper, we introduce a new concept $(\mu_\lambda(v)) - rr$ sequence of a graph, where $\mu_\lambda(v) = rr(\langle \mathcal{N}_\lambda[v] \rangle)$, $v \in V(G)$. In addition, we mainly discuss about the $(\mu_1(v)) - rr$ sequence of a graph. Also, the regularity of $(\mu_1(v)) - rr$ sequence has been studied.

2. The rr Sequence of a Graph:

We have already studied about many sequences such as degree sequence, graphic sequence and so on. Likewise here, we introduce a new sequence based on the radial radio number of a graph.

For a vertex $v \in V(G)$, let $\mu_\lambda(v)$ denote the radial radio number of the induced subgraph induced by $\mathcal{N}_\lambda[v]$. That is, $\mu_\lambda(v) = rr(\langle \mathcal{N}_\lambda[v] \rangle)$. Then the sequence $(\mu_\lambda(v))_{v \in V(G)}$ arranged in decreasing order is called the $(\mu_\lambda(v)) - rr$ sequence of the graph G . The following example gives the $(\mu_1(v)) - rr$ sequence of the graph G .

Example 2.1: Consider the graph G shown in Figure 2.1. The subgraphs induced by $\mathcal{N}_1[v]$, $v \in V(G)$ are also given in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1

Here, $rr(\langle \mathcal{N}_1[v_i] \rangle) = 2, i = 1, 2, 4, 5, 6$ and $rr(\langle \mathcal{N}_1[v_i] \rangle) = 3, i = 3, 7$. Hence the $(\mu_1(v)) - rr$ sequence of G is $(3, 3, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2)$.

In this paper, we mainly discuss about the $(\mu_1(v)) - rr$ sequence of a graph.

A graph G is said to be $\mu - rr$ regular if the $(\mu_1(v)) - rr$ sequence of G is (μ, μ, \dots, μ) , where $\mu = rr(\langle \mathcal{N}_1[u] \rangle)$, for all $u \in V(G)$ and μ is called $rr - constant$.

Figure 2.2

For the graph shown in Figure 2.2, $(\mu_1(v)) - rr$ sequence is $(2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2)$ and hence the graph is $2 - rr$ regular.

A $\mu - rr$ regular graph G is said to be $\mu - rr$ highly regular if $rr(G) = \mu$.

For example, the complete graph K_n is $n - rr$ highly regular and the star graph $K_{1,n}$ is $2 - rr$ highly regular. Wheel graph W_n is $3 - rr$ highly regular, when n is even. Any tree other than $K_{1,n}$ is $2 - rr$ regular but not $2 - rr$ highly regular. The complete bipartite graph $K_{m,n} (m \geq n \geq 2)$ is $2 - rr$ regular but not $2 - rr$ highly regular.

A graph G on n vertices is said to be rr irregular, if it is not $\mu - rr$ regular, for any $\mu, 2 \leq \mu \leq n$.

G

Figure 2.3

For the graph G , shown in Figure 2.3, the $(\mu_1(v)) - rr$ sequence is $(5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 4, 3, 2)$ and hence the graph is rr irregular.

3. Existence of $\mu - rr$ Regular and $\mu - rr$ Highly Regular Graphs:

In this section, we construct graphs with given integer μ as $rr - constant$ and graphs which are $\mu - rr$ regular but not $\mu - rr$ highly regular.

Theorem 3.1: For any given $n \geq 4$, there exists a $n - rr$ regular graph G but not $n - rr$ highly regular.

Proof: The required graph G_n is constructed using the three copies $K_{n-2}, n \geq 4$. Take

$$V(G_n) = \{v, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n-2}, w, w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{n-2}, u, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{n-2}\} \text{ and}$$

$$E(G_n) = \{vw, wu, uv\} \cup \{vv_i, wv_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-2\} \cup \{v_i v_j : 1 \leq i \neq j \leq n-2\}$$

$$\cup \{ww_i, uw_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-2\} \cup \{w_i w_j : 1 \leq i \neq j \leq n-2\}$$

$$\cup \{uu_i, vu_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-2\} \cup \{u_i u_j : 1 \leq i \neq j \leq n-2\}.$$

We have $|V(G_n)| = 3n-3$ and $rad(G) = 2$. The graph G_4 is shown in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1

Now, we have to show that $rr(G_n) \neq rr(\langle N[u] \rangle)$, for any $u \in V(G_n)$.

For $n \geq 6$, define $f : V(G_n) \rightarrow \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ such that

$$f(v) = 1;$$

$$f(v_1) = 4;$$

$$f(v_2) = 7;$$

$$f(v_i) = f(v_{i-1}) + 2, \quad 3 \leq i \leq n-2;$$

$$f(w) = f(v_{n-2}) + 2;$$

$$f(w_1) = 2;$$

$$f(w_2) = 5;$$

$$f(w_3) = 8;$$

$$f(w_i) = f(w_{i-1}) + 2, \quad 4 \leq i \leq \lceil \frac{n-2}{2} \rceil + 1;$$

$$f(w_{\lceil \frac{n-2}{2} \rceil + 2}) = f(w) + 2;$$

$$f(w_i) = f(w_{i-1}) + 2, \quad \lceil \frac{n-2}{2} \rceil + 3 \leq i \leq n-2;$$

$$f(u) = f(w_{\lceil \frac{n-2}{2} \rceil + 1}) + 2;$$

$$f(u_1) = f(u) + 2;$$

$$f(u_i) = f(u_{i-1}) + 2, \quad 2 \leq i \leq n-4;$$

$$f(u_{n-3}) = 6;$$

$$f(u_{n-2}) = 3.$$

The radial radio condition for G_n is

$$d(u, v) + |f(u) - f(v)| \geq 3 \quad (3)$$

for all $u, v \in V(G_n)$. Now, we have to show that f is a radial radio labeling for G_n . To prove this, it is enough to show that every pair of vertices satisfies (3).

Case 1: Consider the pair (u, v) . Since $d(u, v) = 1$, we have $d(u, v) + |f(u) - f(v)| = 1 + |1 - (f(w_{\lceil \frac{n-2}{2} \rceil + 1}) + 2)| \geq 3$.

Thus the pair (u, v) satisfies (3). Similarly, the pairs (v, w) and (w, u) satisfy (3).

Case 2: Consider the pair (v, v_i) , $1 \leq i \leq n-2$. Since $d(v, v_i) = 1$, $d(v, v_i) + |f(v) - f(v_i)| \geq 1 + |1 - 4| \geq 3$. Therefore, the pair (v, v_i) , $1 \leq i \leq n-2$ satisfies (3). Similarly, the pairs (u, u_i) and (w, w_i) , $1 \leq i \leq n-2$ satisfy (3).

Case 3: Consider the pair (v, w_i) , $1 \leq i \leq n-2$. We have $d(v, w_i) = 2$, $d(v, w_i) + |f(v) - f(w_i)| \geq 2 + |1 - 2| \geq 3$. Thus

the pair (v, w_i) , $1 \leq i \leq n-2$ satisfies (3). Similarly, the pairs (w, u_i) and (u, v_i) , $1 \leq i \leq n-2$ satisfy (3).

Case 4: Consider the pair (v, u_i) , $1 \leq i \leq n-2$. Since $d(v, u_i) = 1$, we have $d(v, u_i) + |f(v) - f(u_i)| \geq 1 + |1 - (f(w_{\lceil \frac{(n-2)2+1}{2} \rceil}) + 4)| > 3$ and so the pair (v, u_i) , $1 \leq i \leq n-2$ satisfies (3). Similarly, the pairs (u, w_i) and (w, v_i) , $1 \leq i \leq n-2$ satisfy (3).

Case 5: Consider the pair (v_i, v_j) , $1 \leq i \neq j \leq n-2$. Since $d(v_i, v_j) = 1$ and the label difference between v_i and v_j , $1 \leq i \neq j \leq n-2$ is at least 2, the pair (v_i, v_j) , $1 \leq i \neq j \leq n-2$ satisfies (3). Similarly, we can show that the pairs (u_i, u_j) , (w_i, w_j) , $1 \leq i \neq j \leq n-2$ satisfy (3).

Case 6: Consider the pair (v_i, w_j) , $1 \leq i, j \leq n-2$. Since $d(v_i, w_j) = 2$, $1 \leq i, j \leq n-2$, $d(v_i, w_j) + |f(v_i) - f(w_j)| \geq 2 + |4 - 2| \geq 3$. Therefore, the pair (v_i, w_j) , $1 \leq i, j \leq n-2$ satisfies (3). Similarly, we can prove that the pairs (u_i, w_j) , (u_i, v_j) , $1 \leq i, j \leq n-2$ satisfy (3).

Thus f is a radial radio labeling of G . Also, we have $span(f) = |V(G_n)| = 3n - 3$, $n \geq 6$.

For $n = 4, 5$, radial radio labeling of G_4 and G_5 are given in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2

Hence $rr(G_n) \leq 3n - 3$.

Since $rad(G_n) = diam(G_n)$, G_n is self centered. Thus by Theorem 1.1, we have $rr(G_n) \geq 3n - 3$. Hence, we can conclude that $rr(G_n) = 3n - 3$.

Now, we find $rr(\langle \mathcal{N}_1[u] \rangle)$, for all $u \in V(G_n)$. Here we have two types of vertices:

Type 1: vertex of degree $2n - 2$.

Type 2: vertex of degree $n - 1$.

Let $a \in V(G_n)$. If $deg(a) = 2n - 2$, then $\langle \mathcal{N}_1[a] \rangle \cong G$, where the graph G is given in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3

We have, $rr(G) = n$. Hence $rr(\langle \mathcal{N}_1[a] \rangle) = n$. If $deg(a) = n - 1$, then $\langle \mathcal{N}_1[a] \rangle \cong K_n$. We have, $rr(K_n) = n$ [10] and so $rr(\langle \mathcal{N}_1[a] \rangle) = n$. Hence $rr(\langle \mathcal{N}_1[u] \rangle) = rr(\langle \mathcal{N}_1[v] \rangle)$, for all $u, v \in V(G)$. Thus the $(\mu_1(v)) - rr$ sequence of G_n is (n, n, \dots, n) . But $rr(G_n) = 3n - 3$ and so $rr(G_n) \neq rr(\langle \mathcal{N}_1[u] \rangle)$, for any

$u \in V(G_n)$. Thus G_n is $n-rr$ regular graph but not $n-rr$ highly regular.

Theorem 3.2: For any given integers $m \geq 1$ and $n \geq 2$, there exists a $n-rr$ highly regular graph of order $m(n-1)+1$ with rr – constant n .

Proof: Consider the complete graph K_n , $n \geq 2$. Let G be the required graph. Take $V(G) = \{v, v_1^{(1)}, v_2^{(1)}, \dots, v_{n-1}^{(1)}, v_1^{(2)}, v_2^{(2)}, \dots, v_{n-1}^{(2)}, \dots, v_1^{(m)}, v_2^{(m)}, \dots, v_{n-1}^{(m)}\}$ and $E(G) = \{vv_i^{(j)} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1, 1 \leq j \leq m\} \cup \{v_i^{(j)}v_s^{(j)} : 1 \leq i \neq s \leq n-1, 1 \leq j \leq m\}$. The graph G is shown in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4

Here, we have $\omega = n$ and $rad(G) = 1$.

Define $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ by

$$f(v_i^{(j)}) = i + 1, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n-1, 1 \leq j \leq m;$$

$$f(v) = 1.$$

The radial radio condition for G is

$$d(u, v) + |f(u) - f(v)| \geq 2 \tag{4}$$

for all $u, v \in V(G)$. Now, we have to show that f is a radial radio labeling for G . Here, we have $d(v_i^{(s)}, v_j^{(t)}) = 2$, $1 \leq i \neq j \leq n-1, 1 \leq s \neq t \leq m$. From the definition, $v_i^{(s)}$ and $v_j^{(t)}$, $1 \leq i \neq j \leq n-1, 1 \leq s \neq t \leq m$ have the same labels. By Fact (1), it can be allowed and hence f satisfies (4). Thus f is a radial radio labeling of G . Also, $span(f) = n$. Thus $rr(G) \leq n$. It is already proven that $rr(G) \geq \omega$ [1] and hence $rr(G) \geq n$. Hence $rr(G) = n$.

Now, we find $rr(\langle \mathcal{N}_1[u] \rangle)$, for all $u \in V(G)$. Here we have two types of vertices:

Type 1: vertex of degree $m(n-1)$.

Type 2: vertex of degree $n-1$.

Let $a \in V(G_n)$. If $deg(a) = m(n-1)$, then $\langle \mathcal{N}_1[a] \rangle \cong G$. Hence $rr(\langle \mathcal{N}_1[a] \rangle) = n$. If $deg(a) = n-1$, then $\langle \mathcal{N}_1[a] \rangle \cong K_n$. We have, $rr(K_n) = n$ [10] and so $rr(\langle \mathcal{N}_1[a] \rangle) = n$. Hence $rr(\langle \mathcal{N}_1[u] \rangle) = rr(\langle \mathcal{N}_1[v] \rangle)$, for all $u, v \in V(G)$. Thus the $(\mu_1(v))$ – rr sequence of G is (n, n, \dots, n) and hence G is $n-rr$ regular. But $rr(G) = n$ and so $rr(G) = rr(\langle \mathcal{N}_1[u] \rangle)$, for any $u \in V(G)$. Thus G is $n-rr$ highly regular.

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